

Supporting the Integration of Substance Use Interventions in HIV Service Organizations

Substance use disorders (SUDs) impact every stage of the HIV care continuum, including increased risk of new infections, delayed testing and diagnosis, and reduced adherence to medication and viral suppression.^{1,2} Addressing SUDs among People with HIV is critical to achieving the goals of the “Ending the HIV Epidemic” initiative which aims to reduce new HIV infections in the US by 90% by 2030.³ Integrating SUD interventions into HIV service organizations (HSOs) is key to reaching this goal. Psychosocial interventions, like motivational interviewing, have shown promise for integration into HSOs. Supporting HSOs to implement psychosocial interventions may help them improve outcomes for people with HIV along the HIV care continuum.

The Health Resources and Services Administration’s AIDS Education and Training Center (AETC) Program is a national network of HIV experts who provide training and technical assistance to healthcare providers serving PWH. With eight regional offices and local partners, AETCs could serve as intermediaries to support the integration of effective SUD interventions into HSOs.⁴ Here, we present strategies AETCs can use to enhance the adoption, implementation, and sustainability of evidence-based interventions (EBIs) within HSOs.

◆ Potential Strategies to Support Integration

We engaged HIV, SUD, and implementation practitioners and researchers to identify 10 implementation strategies that some AETCs already use or could use to support HSOs in implementing psychosocial interventions that address substance use (**Figure 1**).

Figure 1. Overview of Implementation Strategies

The strategies have different resource requirements for AETCs to be able to carry them out successfully (e.g., what skills AETC staff would need to deliver the strategy, and the level of financial resources and time an AETC would need to devote to delivering the strategy) (**Table 1**).

Table 1. Approaches to Integrating Implementation Strategies within HSOs

Strategy	Details
EXPLORE	Disseminate EBI Information Increase the HSO’s knowledge about the intervention by identifying intervention-specific resources and sending them to leadership and staff.
	Conduct Formal Assessment Support the HSO in identifying service gaps and interventions to fill unmet needs by assessing community need and HSO readiness to fulfill that need.
	Obtain Formal Commitment Help grow the HSO’s commitment to implementing the intervention by encouraging leadership to commit to implementing the intervention.
PREPARE	Develop Implementation Plan Increase the extent to which the HSO is prepared to implement the intervention by engaging leadership and staff to determine necessary steps to implement.
	Provide Access to Training Modules Bolster the HSO’s understanding and perceptions of the intervention by providing staff with access to online modules and monitoring their completion.
	Conduct Interactive Training Workshop Develop intervention knowledge and skills within the HSO by conducting a workshop with staff that includes experiential exercises.
	Assess Provider Proficiency in EBI Skills Establish intervention competency within the HSO by using fidelity checklists and providing staff with feedback to ensure the intervention is delivered as intended.
IMPLEMENT	Provide Ongoing Clinical Consultation Improve intervention knowledge and skills within the HSO by convening staff in small groups to discuss cases and practice skills.
	Provide Ongoing Implementation Support Support the HSO in resolving implementation challenges by convening meetings with the implementation team and facilitating discussion to identify and address challenges.
	Facilitate Ongoing Learning Collaborative Help establish regular reflection and evaluation of the intervention implementation by convening meetings with implementation teams from several HSO to shares experiences and lessons learned and promote widespread and sustained delivery.

◆ Determining Strategy Fit

We engaged 64 representatives of AETC regional offices and local partners to determine the (a) importance of, (b) feasibility of, (c) readiness to offer, (d) scalability of, (e) pressure to offer, and (f) current need for the 10 strategies.⁵

Most participants (98.4%) agreed that integrating SUD-related services into HSOs is important. However, most reported that these services were currently integrated only to a moderate (52.5%) or minor extent (39.3%) within HSOs in their area and few participants indicated that their AETC is expected (21.7%), supported (40.7%), and rewarded (8.3%) to help HSOs integrate SUD-related services to a great extent.

Figure 2 presents the unadjusted Setting-Strategy Fit Index scores for each strategy, reflecting which ones are more promising for AETCs to use to help HSOs integrate SUD interventions. The figure includes the average contribution of the six items that comprise the index.

Figure 2. Total Setting-Strategy Fit Index Scores and Dimension Contributions

Disseminating information about the evidence-based intervention had the highest ratings for each dimension, resulting in the highest overall score (9.24) and the only strategy that had an unadjusted score that was significantly different from all other strategies. Providing access to asynchronous training ranked second (6.97) and was significantly different from all other strategies except from conducting a formal assessment, which had the third-highest score (6.70).

◆ **Selecting and Using Strategies**

The highest rated strategies (disseminating EBI information and providing training access) are one-direction, asynchronous, and easily sustained but offer limited tailored support. The set of strategies with overall scores in the middle (e.g., formal assessments, synchronous trainings, clinical consultation) require more interaction and resources. The lowest rated strategies (i.e., obtaining a formal commitment, developing an implementation plan, providing ongoing implementation support, and facilitating a learning collaborative) require AETC staff to have strong facilitation skills.

Although no single strategy may be a perfect fit, it's important to balance feasibility with potential impact. Different approaches vary in effectiveness and may contribute in distinct ways to achieving meaningful change. The information presented here on Setting-Strategy Fit can help AETCs consider the best option for their setting.

◆ **References**

1. Azar MM, Springer SA, Meyer JP, et al. A systematic review of the impact of alcohol use disorders on HIV treatment outcomes, adherence to antiretroviral therapy and health care utilization. *Drug Alcohol Depend.* 2010;112(3), 178–193. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.drugalcdep.2010.06.014>
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3. HHS. What is ending the HIV epidemic in the U.S.? Office of Infectious Disease and HIV/AIDS Policy, United States Department of Health and Human Services. Accessed January 14, 2025 from <https://www.hiv.gov/federal-response/ending-the-hiv-epidemic/overview>
4. Proctor E, Hooley C, Morse A, et al. Intermediary/purveyor organizations for evidence-based interventions in the US child mental health: Characteristics and implementation strategies. *Implement Sci.* 2019;14(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13012-018-0845-3>
5. Patel SV, Philbrick SM, Bradshaw M, et al. Supporting integration of substance use interventions in HIV service organizations: Assessing the fit of 10 strategies for AIDS Education and Training Centers to use. *Implement Res Pract.*, 2025;6. <https://doi.org/10.1177/26334895251343647>

Implementation & Sustainment Facilitation Strategy Manual

The Implementation & Sustainment Facilitation (ISF) strategy offers an evidence-informed approach to help organizations adopt, implement, and maintain evidence-based interventions (EBIs). In particular, it has demonstrated effectiveness in helping HIV service organizations and their staff implement the Motivational Interviewing Brief Intervention (MIBI) for people with HIV who have risky substance use.¹ The ISF strategy works by providing a model to improve an organization's implementation climate (i.e., whether an intervention is expected, supported, and rewarded) while fostering a strong relationship between an external Implementation Advisor (IA) and the organization's implementation team.

The ISF manual provides necessary tools and strategies that will help IAs, and the implementation teams they work with, effectively navigate challenges, monitor progress, and create an environment where EBIs can become standard practice. Please note that this manual aims to provide guidance for the ISF specifically and does not go into the broader subject of facilitation.

In this 30-page manual, IAs will first review the foundations of ISF and then how to use the ISF by implementation phase.

✦ Foundations of ISF

Core ISF Strategies and Tools. The first section provides an overview of strategies and tools designed to engage an organization's staff in EBI implementation.

The ISF Relational Framework for Process Implementation. This section explains the four foundational framework elements of the ISF model. Each element illustrates the importance of an IA's role when using key ISF strategies and tools to strengthen the relationship between IAs and the implementation teams with whom they work.

The Four Processes of Motivational Interviewing (MI). Engage, Focus, Evoke, and Plan. This section gives a detailed review of the core MI principles and its four processes, which are referenced throughout the ISF manual. These processes provide an action plan that IAs can use to guide an organization through EBI implementation effectively.

◆ ISF by Implementation Phase

Initial Engagement & Planning. In alignment with the four MI processes, this section introduces tools to evoke reflection on factors that might impact implementation—either positively or negatively. Some tools that IAs will learn to use include the Implementation and Climate Evaluation tool; the Decisional Balance exercise; and Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, Threats or Strengths, Opportunities, Aspirations, Results analyses.

Preparation for Implementation. This section introduces IAs to implementation preparedness through existing resources and mitigating limitations. For example, the Past Implementation Effort exercise is a way to reflect and understand past experience to improve implementation and help teams recognize strengths and overcome barriers. Identifying and preparing champions can ensure prepared support people are “on the ground” to help the implementation effort. Flowcharting can be used to plan for integrating the intervention into existing processes.

Active Implementation & Sustainment Planning. This section focuses on implementing and maintaining strategies through organized data-driven decision-making and consistent team involvement. ISF tools such as the Workbook Tracking Tool and Performance Review and Planning exercise help teams document progress, review performance data, and set clear goals while reinforcing the four MI processes.

◆ Access

The full manual may be accessed in **Appendix B: Roosa M, Garner B. Implementation & Sustainment Facilitation (ISF) Strategy. 2020.**

◆ References

1. Garner BR, Gotham HJ, Chaple M, et al. The implementation and sustainment facilitation strategy improved implementation effectiveness and intervention effectiveness: results from a cluster-randomized, type 2 hybrid trial. *Implement Res Pract.* 2020 Jan-Dec;1:2633489520948073. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2633489520948073>